

Appendix

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Appendix A Search Strategy and Outcome Categories

Table A.1

Keywords

Concept 1		Concept 2		Concept 3		Concept 4		Concept 5
Mindfulness Meditation Mind Body	AND	Workplace Occupational health Employee Worksite Job	AND	Stress, Mental health, Work, performance, Well-being	AND	RCT, randomized controlled trial, randomized controlled trial	NOT	Systematic review, Meta- analysis, review

Table A.2

Description of Outcome categories

Outcome	Subcategories
Stress	Biomarkers: cortisol, alpha amylase, HRV Client related distress Conflicts with nurses Conflicts with physicians Death and dying Distress Distress tolerance Emotional distress Implicit affect Inadequate preparation Job strain Lack of support resources Mental distress Occupational stress Perceived stress Perceived work stressor Personal distress Physical distress Psychological distress Psychological strain Psychological stress Severity of distress Stress symptoms Stressful events Time urgency Uncertainty of treatment Work related stress workload

Mindfulness	Acceptance Acknowledgement Attention regulation Awareness Body listening Calmness Compassion Consciousness Describing Emotional awareness Mindfulness in teaching Non-distracting Nonjudging Nonreactivity Non-worrying Noticing Observing Present moment Present-centered awareness Psychological flexibility Self-compassion Self-regulation Trusting
Burnout	Compassion fatigue Depersonalization Emotional exhaustion Mental distance Personal accomplishment
Well-being	Affect Compassion satisfaction Emotional well-being General mental health / well-being Health complaints Job satisfaction Life purpose Life satisfaction Mental well-being Mental health Psychological quality of life Psychological well-being Quality of life Satisfaction outside work Self-efficacy of coping Well-being

Job performance	Work-life balance
	Work-life conflict
	Work-related well-being
	Absenteeism
	absorption
	Capacity for work
	Classroom management
	Classroom organization
	Contextual performance
	Counter-productive work behavior
	Decreased ability to work
	Dedication
	Instructional practices
	Intention to quit
	Job engagement
	Job rumination
	presenteeism
	Productivity loss
	Self-efficacy
	Student engagement
	Task performance
	Vigor
	Willingness to contribute
	Work engagement
	Work impairment
	Work limitations
	Work motivations
	Work performance

Appendix B Table of Study Description

Table B.1

Table of Characteristics of included Studies

Author, Year	Country	Intervention	Techniques	Comparison	Occupation	Duration	Age	Share of females (%)	Outcomes
Aghamohammadi et al. (2022)	IR	MBSR adapted to culture	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	14	NA	NA	Stress
Aikens et al. (2014)	US	MI	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	7	NA	NA	Mindfulness Stress
Aeschbach et al. (2022)	DE	MBSR adapted to resident physicians	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (Information Control)	2	18	31.02	65.31	Mindfulness Well-being
Alexander et al. (2015)	US	Mindful Yoga	Open monitoring	Active Control (UC)	2	NA	46.38	97.5	Mindfulness Burnout
Alfurjani et al. (2023)	JO	MBSR adaptation – In MBSR adaptation – Out	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	2	30.09	70.3	Mindfulness Stress
Allexandre et al. (2016)	US	Web-based stress management program	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	4	8	40	83.2	Mindfulness Stress Burnout Well-being

Amutio et al. (2015)	ES	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	20	47.31	57.1	Mindfulness Burnout
Ancona und Mendelson (2014b)	US	MI for teachers	Breathing techniques	Passive Control (WL)	2	4.5	38.1	81.4	Stress Burnout
Anderson et al. (1999)	US	Standardized meditation program	Mantra meditation	Passive Control (WL)	2	7.5	NA	84.61	Stress Burnout
Asl (2021)	TR	MBCT adaptation	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	4.68	33.06	55.1	Stress
Asuero et al. (2014)	ES	Mindfulness in everyday activities	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	20	47	92	Mindfulness Burnout
Auserón et al. (2017)	ES	MBSR and MSC adaptation	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	5	20	49	84.4	Mindfulness Stress
Baby et al. (2018)	NZ	Online Mindfulness Course for Pain	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (Communication skill training)	5	NA	46.3	78	Stress
Bartlett et al. (2021)	AU	Smiling Mind Workplace App Smiling Mind Workplace Program	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Inactive Intervention (App)	2	14	48.6	51	Mindfulness Stress Well-being

Bartlett et al. (2016)	AU	MaWP (MBSR adaptation)	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (Information Control)	1	7.5	40.42	82.5	Mindfulness Stress Well-being Job performance
Rice et al. (2024)	US	MBSR-ld MBSR-hd	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	0	12 20	48	46	Mindfulness
Bhandari (2017)	IN	Integrated Yogic Intervention	Mantra meditation	Passive Control (WL)	2	281.6	33.72	0 100	Stress
Bhardwaj et al. (2023)	IN	Yoga based meditation and breath Intervention	Breathing techniques	Passive Control (WL)	2	6	28.26	36.73	Stress Burnout Wellbeing
Biman et al. (2021)	IN	Yoga intervention	Breathing techniques	Passive Control (WL)	7	5212	37.51	54.84	Well-being
Bostock et al. (2018)	GB	Headspace and reflection	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	112	35.5	59.2	Well-being
Brinkmann et al. (2020)	DE	MBSR adaptation with elements of MBCT and compassion	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Active Control (HRV-Biofeedback)	2	210	43.27	71.23	Mindfulness Stress
Burnett and Pettijohn (2015)	US	MBST	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	5.95	39.36	63.6	Stress

				Active Control (relaxation)					
Cheema et al. (2013)	AU	Hatha Yoga	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	3	24.9	38	81.08	Well-being
Chelidoni et al. (2020b)	GB	BuiBase app MT (body scans)	Breathing techniques Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	0.08	32.32	64	Stress
Chin et al. (2018)	US	MT-hd	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (MT-Id)	2	12.6	30.52	66.7	Stress
Christodoulou et al. (2024)	GB	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Inactive Intervention (ACT)	2	7.92	42	77	Mindfulness Stress Job performance
Christopher et al. (2018)	US	MBSR adaptation (mindfulness-based resilience training)	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	5	16	43.97	10	Mindfulness Stress Burnout
Coelhoso et al. (2019)	BR	Well-being app with reflection	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (Perception monitoring)	2	8	34.6	NA	Stress Well-being
Cook et al. (2016)	US	Achiever resilience curriculum	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (Attention control training)	2	12.5	NA	NA	Stress Well-being

Crain et al. (2016)	CA	Workplace mindfulness training	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	35.839	46.9	89	Mindfulness Well-being Job performance
De Bloom et al. (2017)	FI	Relaxation	Breathing techniques	Passive Control (WL) Active Control (walking)	2	6.25	45.5 48.9	90 89.2	Well-being
Desai et al. (2024)	US	Heartfulness meditation	Psycho-emotional focused	Active Control (Gratitude)	2	28.14	45	84.8	Stress Burnout Well-being Job performance
Díaz-Silveira et al. (2020)	ES	MM (MBSR adaptation)	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Active Control (Physical Exercise)	1	10	46.81	67	Stress Well-being
Santos et al. (2021)	BR	Flourish Program	Mantra meditation	Passive Control (WL)	2	12	38.13 43.5	100	Stress
Dwivedi et al. (2015)	IN	Yoga	Breathing techniques	Inactive Intervention (Information Control and physical exercise)	3	50	27.74	45	Well-being
Eriksson et al. (2018)	SE	Mindful self-compassion program	Mantra meditation	Passive Control (WL)	2	9	36.2	98.76	Mindfulness Stress Burnout

Errazuriz et al. (2020)	CL	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Inactive Intervention (Stress management)	2	16	40.2	98.06	Stress
Fazia et al. (2021)	IT	Integral Meditation	Mantra meditation	Passive Control (WL)	2	12	34.09	69.5	Mindfulness Stress Well-being
Fendel et al. (2021)	DE	MBSR adapted to physicians	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (Information control)	2	17.36	31.02	96	Stress Burnout Job performance
Fiol-DeRoque et al. (2021)	ES	PsyCovidApp	NA	Inactive Intervention (Control App)	2	NA	41.37	83.2	Stress Burnout Well-being
Flook et al. (2013)	US	mMBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	20	43.06	88.88	Mindfulness Stress Burnout
Franco et al. (2010)	ES	Flow Meditation	Open monitoring	Active Control (Psychomotor therapy)	2	15	40.2	57.35	Stress
Frank et al. (2013)	US	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	16	40.72	77.8	Mindfulness Burnout
Gan et al. (2024)	CN	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	20	33.21	89.3	Mindfulness Burnout

Da Silva Gherardi-Donato et al. (2023)	BR	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	16	40.95	NA	Mindfulness Stress
Grégoire und Lachance (2014)	CA	MT	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	5	5	35.8	91	Mindfulness Stress
Grégoire et al. (2015)	CA	MT	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	5	5	36.1	58.5	Mindfulness Stress Burnout Well-being
Harris et al. (2015)	US	CALM	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	21.12	43	88	Mindfulness Stress Burnout Well-being Job performance
Hartfiel et al. (2010)	GB	Dru Yoga	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	6 6.64	39.3 44.85	90 89.83	Well-being Stress
Healy et al. (2024)	AU	Compassion-focused therapy	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (Professional Development)	2	NA	NA	91.26	Stress Burnout Well-being
Huang et al. (2015)	TW	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	16	42.55	40.95	Stress

Huberty et al. (2022)	US	Calm app	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	9.52	NA	50.58	Stress Job performance
Ireland et al. (2017)	AU	Mindfulness-education and practice	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	10	26.88	64	Stress Burnout
Janssen et al. (2022)	NL	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	20	49	70.83	Mindfulness Stress Burnout Job performance
Jennings et al. (2017)	US	CARE program	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	30.24	41.5 36	93 84	Mindfulness Stress Burnout Well-being
Jennings et al. (2013)	US	CARE program	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	30.24	36	84	Well-being
Klatt et al. (2016)	DK	Mindfulness in Motion (MBSR adaptation)	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	8	42.9	68.42	Stress Job performance
Klatt et al. (2008)	US	MBSR-Id	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	6	44.96	75.5	Mindfulness Stress
Krick und Felfe (2019)	DE	Mindfulness and Resource-based worksite training	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	5	12	25.96	21.3	Mindfulness Stress Well-being

Krick und Felfe (2024)	DE	Mindfulness and Resource-based worksite training	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Active Control (PMR)	0	12	29.99	49.7	Mindfulness Stress Well-being
Kukihara et al. (2022)	JP	Hatha Yoga MT	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	5	6	47.12 48.71	82.76 89.65	Stress Burnout
Lacerda et al. (2018)	BR	Stress Reduction Program	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	9.04	31.62	54.5	Mindfulness Stress
Laker et al. (2023)	GB	Mind Management Skills for Life Program	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	12	45.14	93.1	Mindfulness Burnout
Yoon et al. (2022)	KR	InMind App	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	4.76	37	40.88	Stress Well-being
Lensen et al. (2024)	NL	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	16	39.4	89.9	Mindfulness Stress Well-being Job performance
Lilly et al. (2019b)	US	Destress 9-1-1	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	4	2.94	NA	81.99	Stress
Lin et al. (2015)	TW	Yoga	Breathing techniques	Active Control (free teatime)	2	12.24	30.92	70	Stress

Lin et al. (2018)	CN	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	16	31.53	93.3	Stress Well-being
Mackenzie et al. (2006)	CA	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	2	46.7	96.66	Burnout Well-being
Malarkey et al. (2012)	US	MBSR-Id	Open monitoring	Active Control (lifestyle education)	2	8	50	98.92	Stress
Manotas et al. (2013)	CO	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	8	39.05	90.36	Mindfulness Stress
Martínez-Borrás et al. (2022)	ES	Mindfulness and Self-Compassion Program	Open monitoring	Active Control (Stress Management)	NA	12	41.93	37.5	Mindfulness Stress Burnout
Masih et al. (2019)	AU	RELAX	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	4	36	66.66	Mindfulness Stress
McConachie et al. (2014)	GB	Acceptance and Mindfulness Workshop	NA	Passive Control (WL)	NA	NA	43	74.2	Mindfulness Stress Well-being
Mellner et al. (2022)	SE	MBSR + SIY	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	1	20	45.47	57.5	Mindfulness Well-being

Michel et al. (2014)	DE	MBI	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	2.01	NA	NA	Mindfulness Well-being
Mistretta et al. (2018)	US	Mindfulness-based resilience training	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Active Control (Resilience App)	2	12	46	86.7	Stress Burnout Well-being
Molek-Winiarska und Żołnierczyk- Zreda (2018)	PL	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	8	32	40.36	0	Stress
Möltner et al. (2017)	DE	7 mind	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	NA	42.8	69	Mindfulness Burnout Well-being Job performance
Nadler et al. (2020)	US	MBI	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	249.6	NA	73.53	Mindfulness Stress Well-being
Pizutti et al. (2019)	BR	Mindfulness for Stress program	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Active Control (relaxation)	2	16	41.6	95.2	Mindfulness Well-being
Querstret et al. (2016)	GB	Online mindfulness course	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	NA	40.67	80.51	Mindfulness

Radin et al. (2025)	US	headspace	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	9.52	35.54	80.8	Mindfulness Stress Burnout Job performance
Rao et al. (2017)	IN	Mind sound resonance technique	Mantra meditation	Passive Control (WL)	2	107.5	41.5	100	Stress
Reis et al. (2024)	DE	MT	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Active Control (CBI)	NA	5.22	40.56	75.57	Stress
Rich et al. (2021)	GB	Headspace	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	NA	NA	69.6	Mindfulness Stress Well-being Job performance
Roeser et al. (2021)	US	Mindfulness-Based Emotional Balance	Psycho-emotional focused	Passive Control (WL)	2	28	41.23	69	Mindfulness Stress Burnout Job performance
Safaeian et al. (2023)	IR	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Active Control (Schema therapy)	2	8	NA	100	Burnout
Sawyer et al. (2023)	US	MT	Psycho-emotional focused	Passive Control (WL)	2	13.5	44.37	87.01	Mindfulness Stress Burnout

									Well-being Job performance
Schroeder et al. (2016b)	US	Mindful Medicine Curriculum (MBSR adaptation)	NA	Passive Control (WL)	2	16.98	42.76	73	Mindfulness Stress Burnout
Sheppard et al. (1997)	US	Transcendental Meditation	Mantra meditation	Active Control (Stress Management)	3	10.98	50.5	85	Mindfulness
Shonin et al. (2014)	GB	Meditation Awareness Training	NA	Inactive Intervention (Information control)	1	12	40.03	56.9	Stress Well-being Job performance
Slutsky et al. (2018)	US	MT-hd	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (MT-Id)	NA	12.6	30.52	66.7	Well-being
Sood et al. (2011)	US	Stress Management and Resiliency Training	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	12	48.5	52.5	Stress Well-being
Sood et al. (2014)	US	Stress Management and Resiliency Training	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	12	47.75	42.31	Mindfulness Stress Well-being
Steinberg et al. (2016)	US	MBI	NA	Passive Control (WL)	2	8	44.05	88	Well-being Job performance

Strauss et al. (2021)	GB	MBCT-L	NA	Passive Control (WL)	2	16	43.94	82.91	Mindfulness Stress Burnout Well-being Job performance
Strub und Tarquinio (2013)	LU	MBCT	NA	Passive Control (WL)	NA	16	NA	40	Stress Burnout
Tagg (2015)	US	Brief Mindfulness Intervention	NA	Active Control (Applied behavior analysis)	2	2	NA	NA	Stress Burnout
Talebiazar et al. (2024)	IR	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	16	29.88	51.67	Stress Burnout
Taylor et al. (2015)	CA	Mindfulness training	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	37.26	NA	89.83	Mindfulness Stress
Taylor et al. (2021)	US	Mindfulness program	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	6	42.77	95.8	Stress Burnout
Trombka et al. (2021)	BR	MBHP	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	5	NA	42.26	74.7	Mindfulness
Tsang et al. (2021)	HK	.b Foundations	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	12	39.54	72.58	Mindfulness Stress Well-being

Vainre et al. (2024)	GB	Be Mindful MBP	Open monitoring	Active Control (Physical exercise)	2	NA	44.63	81.93	Mindfulness Stress Job performance
Van Berkel et al. (2014)	NL	Mindful VIP Intervention	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (Information Control)	NA	30.51	45.55	67.32	Mindfulness Job performance
Verdes-Montenegro-Atalaya et al. (2021)	ES	MBSR + MSC	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	10	10.61	76.79	Stress
Versluis et al. (2018)	NL	worry reduction Ecological momentary intervention	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL) Active control (emotion registration)	NA	NA	43.23	71	Mindfulness Stress
Verweij et al. (2017)	NL	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	20	31.2	88	Mindfulness Burnout Well-being Job performance
Wang et al. (2024)	CN	guided self-help MBI	Open monitoring	Inactive Intervention (Information control)	2	16.8	31.85	87.88	Mindfulness Burnout
Wilson (2012)	US	Mindfulness-based art processing MBSR-Id	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	8	NA	66.25	Mindfulness Stress Well-being

									Job performance
Wolever et al. (2012)	US	Viniyoga Stress Reduction Program MT MT (online)	Breathing techniques NA	Passive Control (WL)	NA	12	42.87	76.57	Mindfulness Stress Job performance
Xiang-Zi und Jia-Yuan (2022)	CN	MBI	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	12.8	29.72	72.72	Burnout
Xie et al. (2020)	CN	MBIB	NA	Inactive Intervention (Information Control)	2	20	27.7	100	Mindfulness Burnout
Xu et al. (2021)	AU	Headspace	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	4.76	NA	78	Mindfulness Stress Burnout Well-being
Yang et al. (2018)	CN	MBSR	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	2	NA	29.2	67.37	Stress
Yıldırım und Yıldız (2022)	TR	Mindfulness-based breathing and music therapy	Open monitoring	Active Control (Relaxation)	2	0.5	28.33	50	Stress Well-being
Yoon et al. (2022b)	KR	InMind App	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	NA	14	37	26.67	Stress Well-being

Żolnierczyk-Zreda et al. (2016)	PL	MBI	Open monitoring	Passive Control (WL)	1	24	39.4	49	Stress Job performance
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Appendix C Review outcomes: Graphs and Analysis

- C1** Review of Stress Outcome (p. 22)
- C2** Review of Mindfulness Outcome (p. 29)
- C3** Review of Burnout Outcome (p. 35)
- C4** Review of Well-being Outcome (p. 41)
- C5** Review of Job performance Outcome (p. 48)

C1.1 Stress Post-Intervention

C1.1.1 Forest Plot

C1.1.2 Funnel Plot

C1.1.3 Baujat Plot

C1.1.4 Egger's Regression test

$z = -2.339$, $p = 0.019$, $b = -0.066$, $CI [-0.212, 0.345]$

C1.1.5 Influence Plot

C1.2 Stress Follow-Up

C1.2.1 Forest Plot

C1.2.2 Funnel Plot

C1.2.3 Baujat Plot

C1.2.4 Egger's Regression test

$z = -0.335$, $p = 0.737$, $b = -0.170$, CI $[-0.767, 0.427]$

C1.2.5 Influence Plot

C2.1 Mindfulness Post-Intervention

C2.1.1 Forest Plot

C2.1.2 Funnel Plot

C2.1.3 Baujat Plot

C2.1.4 Egger's Regression test

$z = 0.933, p = 0.351, b = 0.254, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.017, 0.526]$

C2.1.5 Influence Plot

C2.2 Mindfulness Follow-Up

C2.2.1 Forest Plot

C2.2.2 Funnel Plot

C2.2.3 Baujat Plot

C2.2.4 Egger's Regression test

$Z = 3.918$, $p < 0.000$, $b = -1.368$, CI $[-2.305, -0.430]$

C2.2.5 Influence Plot

C3.1 Burnout Post-Intervention

C3.1.1 Forest Plot

C3.1.2 Funnel Plot

C3.1.3 Baujat Plot

C3.1.4 Egger's Regression test

$z = -1.987, p = 0.047, b = -0.040, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.204, 0.285]$

C3.1.5 Influence Plot

C3.2 Burnout Follow-Up

cC3.2.1 Forest Plot

C3.2.2 Funnel Plot

C3.2.3 Baujat Plot

C3.2.4 Egger's Regression test

$z = -1.221, p = 0.222, b = 0.077, CI [-0.445, 0.599]$

C3.2.5 Influence Plot

C.4.1 Well-being Post-Intervention

C4.1.1 Forest Plot

C4.1.2 Funnel Plot

C4.1.3 Baujat Plot

C4.1.4 Egger's Regression test

$z = 0.560$, $p = 0.576$, $b = 0.264$, 95% CI [-0.025, 0.552]

C4.1.5 Influence Plot

C.4.2 Well-being Follow-Up

C4.2.1 Forest Plot

C4.2.2 Funnel Plot

C4.2.3 Baujat Plot

C4.2.4 Egger's Regression test

$z = 0.896, p = 0.370, b = 0.032, CI [-0.488, 0.553]$

C4.2.5 Influence Plot

C.5.1 Job performance Post-Intervention

C5.1.1 Forest Plot

C5.1.2 Funnel Plot

C5.1.3 Baujat Plot

C5.1.4 Egger's Regression test

$z = 3.095$, $p = 0.002$, $b = -0.737$, 95% CI $[-1.471, -0.003]$

C5.1.5 Influence Plot

C.5.2 Job performance Follow-Up

C5.2.1 Forest Plot

C5.2.2 Funnel Plot

C5.2.3 Baujat Plot

C5.2.4 Egger's Regression test

$z = 0.597$, $p = 0.551$, $b = 0.069$, CI $[-0.624, 0.762]$

C5.2.5 Influence Plot

Appendix D Graphical display of Evidence Gaps

Figure D.1

Outcomes distributed across the World

Figure D.2*Interventions distributed across the World*

Appendix E Meta-analytic effect estimates Post-Intervention and Follow-up

Table E.1

Meta-analytic effect estimates post intervention and follow-up

Outcome	k	SMD	95% confidence interval		Q	Heterogeneity		
			Lower limit	Upper limit		τ^2	I ² (%)	H ²
<i>Post Intervention</i>								
Stress	140	0.380***	0.286	0.474	706.192	0.255	86.51	7.42
Mindfulness	97	0.376***	0.2867	0.466	401.874	0.141	77.22	4.39
Burnout	46	0.275***	0.181	0.369	88.174	0.042	49.71	1.99
Well-Being	73	0.341***	0.247	0.436	237.683	0.112	73.38	3.76
Job performance	41	0.358*	0.083	0.633	313.639	0.756	96.31	27.13
<i>Follow-Up</i>								
Stress	51	0.266**	0.077	0.456	374.184	0.413	92.42	13.19
Mindfulness	38	0.402*	0.018	0.786	309.040	1.388	97.30	37.05
Burnout	16	0.239***	0.101	0.378	16.965	0.015	19.38	1.24
Well-Being	28	0.260***	0.110	0.410	91.256	0.111	72.91	3.69
Job performance	18	0.270**	0.074	0.467	75.857	0.135	81.63	5.44

***p < .001; **p < .01; *p < .05

Appendix F Table of Moderator Analysis

Table F.1

Moderator Analyses sample, intervention, context, and design characteristics

	Stress			Mindfulness			Burnout			Well-being			Job performance							
	<i>k</i>	<i>Q</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>Q</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>Q</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>Q</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>Q</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Sample																				
age	123	2.268	1	0.132	89	2.518	1	0.113	40	3.895	1	0.048	63	0.493	1	0.483	31	0.546	1	0.460
gender	132	0.097	1	0.755	94	1.264	1	0.261	45	6.799	1	0.009	69	0.889	1	0.346	41	6.496	1	0.011
profession	108	3.767	5	0.583	80	1.714	5	0.887	43	0.326	2	0.850	59	14.225	6	0.027	28	13.647	1	<.000
Intervention																				
type	140	3.372	4	0.498	97	6.455	4	0.168	46	3.391	4	0.495	73	6.647	4	0.156	41	4.583	4	0.333
technique	126	2.265	3	0.520	88	1.140	3	0.767	40	1.127	3	0.771	68	4.383	3	0.223	34	0.220	2	0.896
duration	125	0.030	1	0.862	88	0.84	1	0.360	42	0.014	1	0.906	68	1.655	1	0.198	35	0.970	1	0.325
practice	96	1.023	1	0.312	73	1.381	1	0.240	31	0.054	1	0.817	50	2.473	1	0.116	27	0.034	1	0.853
location	129	9.078	2	0.011	89	3.290	2	0.193	42	1.805	2	0.406	69	4.993	2	0.082	41	0.697	2	0.706
instruction	124	5.390	3	0.145	85	2.048	3	0.563	38	2.503	2	0.286	63	8.611	3	0.035	39	8.252	2	0.016
setting	132	5.060	1	0.025	90	1.712	1	0.191	42	0.758	1	0.384	70	4.994	1	0.025	41	0.404	1	0.525
delivery	135	11.676	3	0.009	93	2.856	3	0.414	44	1.215	3	0.750	70	6.073	3	0.108	41	0.867	3	0.834
Context																				
power																				
distance	139	8.066	1	0.005	95	0.289	1	0.591	46	9.329	1	0.002	73	40.009	1	0.926	41	46.513	1	<.000
individualism	139	3.405	1	0.065	95	0.218	1	0.641	46	10.976	1	0.001	73	0.187	1	0.665	41	9.078	1	0.003

masculinity	139	2.202	1	0.138	95	0.307	1	0.580	46	0.012	1	0.913	73	2.367	1	0.124	41	0.3765	1	0.540
uncertainty avoidance	139	0.124	1	0.725	95	7.131	1	0.008	46	0.043	1	0.837	73	8.020	1	0.005	41	21.072	1	<.000
long-term orientation	139	0.020	1	0.887	95	3.296	1	0.070	46	0.009	1	0.925	73	1.959	1	0.162	41	0.252	1	0.615
indulgence	139	2.518	1	0.113	95	1.306	1	0.253	46	10.282	1	0.001	73	0.093	1	0.760	41	16.061	1	<.000
income group	140	12.529	2	0.002	97	11.664	2	0.003	46	23.167	2	<.001	73	4.943	2	0.085				
country	140	19.286	21	0.567	97	25.484	13	0.020	46	59.491	11	<.000	73	36.759	57	<.000	41	169.648	7	<.000
Design																				
control	140	5.283	2	0.071	97	4.348	2	0.114	46	2.244	2	0.326	73	1.995	2	0.369	41	0.860	2	0.651
measurement	140	36.771	37	0.480	97	20.259	14	0.122	46	1.637	8	0.990	73	78.785	30	<.000	41	11.253	18	0.883
publication date	140	0.000	1	0.994	97	0.762	1	0.383	46	1.555	1	0.212	73	0.973	1	0.324	41	1.016	1	0.314
initiation date	86	0.170	1	0.680	60	2.111	1	0.146	28	2.244	1	0.134	44	1.517	1	0.218	21	1.790	1	0.181

Note. k = number of outcomes, Q = Cochran's Q heterogeneity statistic of moderation, df = degree of freedom of Cochran's Q

Appendix G PRISMA Checklist

Table G.1

PRISMA Checklist (Page et al., 2021)

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	p. 1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	p. 3
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	p. 4 – 8
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	p. 8
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	p. 8 – 9
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	p. 9, 14
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	p. 14
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	p. 9 – 10
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	p. 9 – 10
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	p. 10 – 12
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	p. 10 – 12
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	-
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	p. 12 – 13
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	p. 9 – 10
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data	p. 12 – 13

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
		conversions.	
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	p. 12 – 13
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	p. 12 – 13
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	p. 12 – 13
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	p. 12 – 13
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	-
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	p. 12 – 13
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	p. 13
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	p. 14
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Appendix B
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	-
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Appendix E – F
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	p. 18 – 24
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	p. 18 – 24
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	p. 18 – 24
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	-
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Appendix E – F
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	p. 24 – 30
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	p. 30 – 31

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	p. 30 – 31
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	p. 30 – 32
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	-
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	-
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	-
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	-
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	-
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	p. 32

Appendix H Abbreviations

Table H.1

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AAQ-II	Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II
AJIGS	Abridged Job in General Scale
AQoL	8-dimension Assessment of Quality of Life
ASRES	Affective Self -Regulatory Efficacy Scale
BBI	Bergen Burnout Inventory
BIAJS	Brief Index of Affective Job Satisfaction
BMI	Body Movement Intervention
BRS	Brayfield-Rothe Scale
CAMA	Community Augmented Meta Analysis
CAMS-R	Cognitive and Affective Mindfulness Scale-Revised
CARD	Classroom Appraisal of Resources and Demands
CBI	Copenhagen Burnout Inventory
CBI	Cognitive Behavior Interventions
CHQ-12	Chinese Health Questionnaire
CLASS-S	Classroom Assessment Scoring System-Secondary
CMIHQ	Cornell Medical Index Health Questionnaires
COMOSWB	Concise Measure of Subjective Well-Being
CORE-OM	Clinical Outcomes in Routine Evaluation-Outcomes Measure
CSIS	Context specific indicators of stress
C-SOSI	Calgary Symptoms of Stress Inventory
DASS-21	Depression Anxiety Stress Scales-21
DTS	Distress Tolerance Scale
ERI	Effort Reward Imbalance questionnaire
FFM	Five Factor Mindfulness Questionnaire
FFMQ	Five Facets of Mindfulness Questionnaire
FMI	Freiburg Mindfulness Inventory
GHQ-12	General Health Questionnaire
GSE	General Self-Efficacy Scale
HRV	Heart rate variability
iMTA PCQ	Institute for Medical Technology Assessment Productivity Cost Questionnaire
IPANAT	Implicit Positive and Negative Affect Test
IPPA	Inventory of Positive Psychological Attitudes
IS	Irritations Skala
ISSL	Lipp Stress Symptom Inventory
ITSC	Inventory of Teacher Stress and Coping
IWPQ	Individual Work Performance Questionnaire
JBS	Japanese Burnout Scale

JCQ	Job content questionnaire
JD-R	Job Demands-Resources Model
JES	Job Engagement Scale
JSS	Job Satisfaction Scale
K10	Kessler Psychological Distress Scale
LASA	Linear Analog Self-Assessment Scale
LS	Likert Scale
MAAS	Mindful Attention and Awareness Scale
MAIA	Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness
MaWP	Mindfulness at Work Program
MBCT	Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy
MBCT-L	Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy - low
MBHP	Mindfulness-based health promotion
MBI	Maslach Burnout Inventory
MBI	Mindfulness-based Interventions
MBIB	Mindfulness-based Intervention
MBP	Mindfulness-based Program
MBSR	Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction
MBSR-hd	Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction – high dose
MBSR-ld	Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction – low dose
MBST	Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction Therapy
MHC	Mental Health Continuum
MM	Mindful Meditation
mMBSR	Modified Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction
MMSS	The McCloskey/Mueller Satisfaction Scale
MSC	Mindfulness-SelfCompassion
MT	Mindfulness Training
MT-hd	Mindfulness Training – high dose
MT-ld	Mindfulness Training – low dose
MTS	Mindfulness in Teaching Scale
NSS	Nursing stress scale (Gary Taft and Anderson)
OCB	Organizational citizenship behavior
OLBI	Oldenburg Burnout Inventory
OSI-2	Occupational Stress Indicator
PANAS	Positive Affect Negative Affect Scale
PBNK	psychosomatische Beschwerden im nichtklinischen Kontext
PDMWS	Psychological Distress Manifestations at Work Scale
PICO+S	Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses
ProQOL	Professional Quality of Life Scale
PSM-9	Psychological Stress Measure
PSQ	Perceived Stress Questionnaire

PSS	Perceived Stress Scale
PWBMWS	Psychological Well-being Manifestations at Work Scale
PWBS	Psychological Well-Being Scale
QOL	Quality of life
RBPS	Role-Based Performance Scale
RMSSD	Root mean square of successive differences
SA-45	Symptom Assessment-45 Questionnaire
SCBCS	Santa Clara Brief Compassion Scale
SCL-90-R	Symptom Checklist-90-R
SCS	Self-Compassion Scale
SERIS	Siegrist Effort-Reward Imbalance Scale
SES	Self-Efficacy Scale
SF-36	Short Form-36
SIY	Search inside yourself program
SMBM	Shirom-Melamed Burnout Measure
SMBQ	Shirom Melamed Burnout Questionnaire
SOCS	Sussex-Oxford Compassion Scales
SOSS	Stress Overload Scale Short
SPWB	Scales of Psychological Well-being
SSQ	Staff perception of work stressors
STAI-I	State Anxiety Inventory
SVF 120	stress-coping questionnaire
SWEMWBS	Short Warwick Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale
SWLS	Satisfaction With Life Scale
SWWS	Satisfaction with Work Scale
TICS-SSCS	Trierer Inventar zum chronischen Stress
TSCS	Tennessee Self-Concept Scale
TSES	Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale
TSI	Teacher Stress Inventory
UBOS-L	Utrecht Burnout Scale-Education
UWES	Utrecht Work Engagement Scale
WEMWBS	Warwick Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale
WHO-5	World Health Organization Well-Being Index
WHOQOL	World Health Organization Quality of Life
WLB	Work-life balance 3 point scale
WLCS	Work–Life Conflict Scale
WMF-E	Work Motivation Form-Employee
WPAI	Work Productivity and Activity Impairment
WRFQ	Work Role Functioning Questionnaire
WRSS	work-related stress scale
WSI	indice de stress au travail de Légeron (2003)
WSIT	HSE Management Standards Work-Related Stress Indicator Tool
